

TEACHING CHILDREN TO SAVE – THE FIRST STEP TO ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of the family in teaching a child to be thrifty, as a first step towards thrift and entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Thrift, family, preschool, school, entrepreneurship.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль семьи в обучении ребенка бережливости, как первому шагу к бережливости и предприимчивости.

Ключевые слова: Бережливость, семья, дошкольное учреждение, школа, предпринимательство.

The earliest ideas about economic education and upbringing date back nearly 3,000 years in our homeland, reflected in the sacred book of Zoroastrianism, the Avesta, which was left to us as a legacy by the great scholar and philosopher Zoroaster. Although this work was originally written based on religious views, it also embodies early ideas related to various fields. In fact, many concepts and ideas that are recognized as having been first studied in Ancient Greece were actually created earlier and are reflected in this unique book.

Economic upbringing should, first and foremost, begin within the family. One of its essential conditions is the attitude toward money within the household. A.S. Makarenko, in his book *“For Parents,”* highlights three types of attitudes toward money. In the first case, the head of the family says: “Immorality has increased everywhere, and all children have money jingling in their pockets.” In the second case, another head of the family argues: “Adults are only busy counting money, and children should be raised away from such harmful things.” The third perspective is expressed by an accountant, who states: “A family is an economy; money comes in and is spent.”

Is economic education necessary for preschool children, and why? This question has become particularly relevant today and requires serious pedagogical reconsideration. The more preschool children interact with social reality and everyday life, the more questions arise in their minds. Daily life, family environment, communication with peers, and educational activities in preschool institutions form the foundation for further economic education. In this process,

the preschool teacher becomes an authoritative figure who helps the child correctly understand new phenomena, facts, and concepts.

The economic well-being of a family largely depends on the employment of its able members, their entrepreneurial activities, knowledge, and abilities. Since family economy consists of property acquired through labor and material goods accumulated through thrift, economic knowledge plays an important role in creating and managing these resources.

Economic knowledge serves not only the individual and their family but also contributes to the prosperity of society as a whole.

Thrift is a distinctive aspect of care and responsibility. While care may remain in a person's thoughts, thrift is manifested in daily habits. A person may be a caring head of the household but still lack thriftiness. Therefore, it is necessary to cultivate this quality from an early age within the family. This habit should begin with eating behavior—teaching children not to waste food, not to damage toys, and to keep their clothes clean. Of course, instilling these habits is difficult, but it is essential to develop them in children despite the challenges. Otherwise, mere verbal instruction will have little effect.

Children should always be encouraged to be thrifty. They should be taught not only to take care of their own belongings but also to respect others' property and protect the environment. In shaping a child's economic thinking, it is important not only to teach thrift and careful use of resources but also to guide them in making *правиль* decisions.

The search for optimal ways to solve the problem of economic education of preschool children has led to the use of game technologies. Among various types of games, economically oriented didactic games are particularly important.

The following game activity can be used to reinforce children's knowledge about entrepreneurship:

“What Are the Sources of Income?” Objective: To strengthen children's economic knowledge; clarify their understanding of main and additional sources of income; and develop skills in distinguishing between different types of income.

Materials: Cards illustrating main occupations that generate primary income (e.g., hairdresser, doctor, carpenter, tailor, weaver, etc.), as well as activities that provide additional income through natural products (e.g., collecting berries and mushrooms, gardening, horticulture, etc.).

Procedure: Children are divided into groups. One child from each group selects a card and shares their thoughts based on it. They name the occupation, describe the result, and distinguish between primary and additional income. They

also talk about what type of activity they would like to engage in in the future and how they could earn additional income. Other group members then continue the game in the same way.

Conclusion

Achieving results in the economy is directly related to thrift. Therefore, children should be taught from an early age about family economy, income and expenses, and financial management. Special attention should be given to developing entrepreneurial skills in children. Over time, they will learn how to manage a household and take responsibility for its economic well-being. Economic views formed in childhood encourage individuals to find ways to ensure family prosperity. The foundation of economic education for preschool children is closely linked with moral and labor education. For this reason, state educational programs place great importance on economic upbringing.

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